

DIGITAL READING BEHAVIOR THROUGH THE ANGLE OF ENGLISH MAJOR STUDENTS: A PHENOMENOLOGICAL INQUIRY

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Digital Reading Behavior through the Angle of English Major Students: A Phenomenological Inquiry

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Abstract

This qualitative study examines the digital reading behaviors of 20 English major students at St. John Paul II College of Davao, focusing on their preferences, challenges, and the implications of digital reading for academic engagement. The study uses semi-structured interviews and thematic analysis to examine how digital tools influence students' reading comprehension, retention, and overall learning experience. The findings reveal a difficult interaction between the accessibility and convenience of digital resources and challenges such as distractions and eye strain, which impact learning outcomes. This research aims to provide educators and curriculum developers with insights on integrating digital reading practices in English language studies to improve students' learning efficacy. The study contributes to the growing understanding of digital reading behaviors in an educational setting.

Keywords: *digital reading, english major students, reading behavior, phenomenology, digital literacy*

Introduction

In a rapidly digitalize world, the way we read and engage with text has transformed significantly, especially within academic contexts. Numerous studies have found a rise in screen-based reading due to the popularity of e-books (Picton, 2014) and digital texts have changed how students read today. Globally, digital reading has gained traction due to the accessibility and convenience it offers, impacting students' reading habits and learning processes. The OECD (2016) highlights that screen-based reading is now a primary mode of engagement, leading to different reading behaviors, such as non-linear reading and frequent skimming, compared to traditional print reading. Such behaviors, while conducive to quick information retrieval, often challenge deep comprehension and retention, raising concerns about the long-term cognitive effects on students worldwide. Digital reading provides instant access to a wealth of information that helps with comprehension according to (Liu, 2012). As digital resources become integral to educational systems, understanding the nuanced impact of digital reading on student learning has become crucial across disciplines.

Nationally, the Philippines has observed a swift adoption of digital technology in education, catalyzed by the shift to online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic. Despite this, digital reading remains challenging for Filipino students, many of whom face limited access to reliable digital resources and encounter issues with screen fatigue and information overload (Acosta, 2022). Furthermore, Kaufman and Flanagan (2016) found that students reading digitally did well on answering concrete questions. Additionally, Pardede (2019) highlights that the proliferation of digital reading devices has reduced paper usage in classrooms, and tablet ownership is higher among those with higher education levels. Moreover, Studies in the Philippines show that while students appreciate the accessibility of digital materials, they also report difficulties with digital comprehension and retention, which can hinder their academic performance and critical thinking skills. Recognizing these national challenges underscores the need for targeted research to explore Filipino students' specific experiences and strategies in digital reading.

At the local level, within Davao City, digital reading behaviors among English major students have yet to be thoroughly examined. English majors, in particular, rely heavily on extensive reading for literary and linguistic studies, making them a critical group to study in the context of digital reading. Local educational institutions, such as St. John Paul II College of Davao, are adapting to technological shifts, but a lack of localized research leaves a gap in understanding how digital reading affects students' academic engagement and comprehension at the community level. In line with that, Hampel and Pleines (2013) concluded that there are many challenges of online learning in terms of the skills that both teachers and learners need to develop to deal with the pedagogical, cognitive and socio affective implications of electronic communication. Teachers in a technology-driven world should carefully choose programs that promote student engagement.

This study fills a significant gap in understanding about the digital reading habits of English major students in the Philippines, especially in areas with restricted access to digital resources, which is why we researchers are interested in carrying it out. In order to create equitable and successful digital literacy programs, teachers and administrators can benefit greatly from investigating their preferences, habits, and the effects on academic achievement as suggested by Liu (2012). Furthermore, the COVID-19 pandemic's increased use of digital tools emphasizes how urgent it is to look at these practices in order to create learning environments that address challenges like overload of information, fatigue from screens, and accessibility concerns (Acosta, 2022).

Addressing this gap could help educators and policymakers create resources and instructional strategies that support students' reading comprehension and literacy in a digital age. Additionally, previous research needs to pay more attention to the actual experiences of English major students in favor of focusing on broader student groups or specific technologies. While studies like Pardede (2020) and Soroya and Ameen (2016) highlight the impact of digital texts on student learning and engagement, they fail to consider the local educational, technological, and cultural factors that influence these experiences.

This study is framed by Pirolli and Card's Information Foraging Theory (1999), which likens information-seeking behavior to food foraging, wherein individuals adapt strategies based on information "value" and accessibility. This theory is particularly relevant for understanding how students manage digital information overload and search for relevant material amid the vast digital landscape. Complemented by Thorndike's Law of Learning Theory (1984), which emphasizes repetition and readiness in effective learning, these frameworks guide our exploration of English major students' digital reading behaviors, challenges, and strategies for comprehension.

Research Questions

This study aimed to address the following key questions regarding the digital reading behavior of English major students:

1. What is the extent of the reading behavior of the participants on digital materials?
2. How do electronic instructional materials improve the reading behavior of the students?
3. What suggestions or recommendations could they share with their classmates in attaining positive reading behavior?

Literature Review

Reading Habits of Students Using Electronic Books

The shift to digital reading has prompted researchers to investigate how students engage with electronic texts. According to Pardede (2019), students often favor e-books due to their accessibility and variety of features, such as search functions and adjustable text sizes. Hassan et al. (2021) found that digital reading fosters positive habits among secondary school students, enhancing their motivation to read. Conversely, Kannianen et al. (2019) observed that struggling readers may experience challenges, such as difficulty concentrating and fatigue, when reading from screens. Research by Chen et al. (2021) supports this, highlighting that while e-books are beneficial, they may not be universally embraced due to varying individual preferences and reading capabilities.

Internet and Electronic Content Influence Student Reading

The internet has dramatically transformed reading behaviors, with an increasing amount of time spent on digital content (Kurata et al., 2016). Rapid information dissemination, vastly improved opportunities for social interaction, and countless other advantages have all resulted from the advent of the digital age (Sarica et al., 2016). Grzeschik et al. (2011) also highlighted that digital reading does not significantly hinder reading speed or comprehension but emphasizes the need for effective strategies to navigate online materials. This transition to digital formats can lead to a decline in traditional print reading, which is supported by findings from Sarica et al. (2016), who noted the declining subscriptions to print newspapers as more individuals choose for online news sources.

Factors Influencing Digital Reading Behavior

Numerous factors influence how students approach digital reading, ranging from personal preferences to environmental contexts. According to Divya and Haneefa (2020), psychological factors such as motivation and prior experience with technology significantly affect reading habits. Soroya and Ameen (2018) suggest that the availability of diverse digital resources encourages students to read more frequently. Furthermore, research by Pardede (2019) indicates that the ease of access to information on digital platforms often results in an increased willingness to engage with various texts, while other studies emphasize the impact of social and peer influences on reading behaviors.

Web-based Digital Reading Annotations

Digital reading platforms have introduced tools that enhance the reading experience, such as annotations and highlighting features. Chen et al. (2014) found that these tools can improve comprehension and retention of information. Akçapnar et al. (2019) highlighted the importance of collaborative annotation, where students share insights and perspectives to deepen their understanding of the text. Research by Yang et al. (2020) supports this notion, demonstrating that annotation tools can facilitate better learning outcomes by encouraging engagement and critical thinking among students.

The Impact of E-Reading on Reading Ability

Research on the effects of e-reading on reading abilities is mixed, with some studies indicating advantages and others showing limitations. Mangen et al. (2013) found that students who read printed texts performed better on comprehension tests than those who read digitally. However, Aydemir et al. (2013) reported no significant difference in performance between digital and print reading in their sample. This discrepancy may arise from factors such as students' familiarity with digital formats and their reading strategies (Dillon, 1994). The need for effective instructional strategies to support digital reading is underscored by Guzmán-Simón et al. (2017), who advocate for integrating digital literacy into academic curricula.

The Views of Students and Educators on Electronic Texts

Understanding perceptions of digital reading among students and educators is crucial for successful implementation in academic settings. Anuradha and Usha (2006) found that a significant majority of e-book users report satisfaction with their digital reading experiences. However, Shelburne (2009) noted that while students tend to favor e-books, educators often have reservations about their effectiveness. This gap highlights the necessity for ongoing dialogue between students and educators to align educational practices

with evolving reading behaviors. Research by Lim and Hew (2014) indicates that fostering positive attitudes toward e-books can enhance their integration into teaching practices, ultimately benefiting student learning.

Methodology

Participants

The participants in this study consisted of 20 English major students from St. John Paul II College of Davao. A purposive sampling method was used to select participants who met specific criteria: they had to be officially enrolled in the second semester of the Academic Year 2022-2023, be 18 years old or older, and have experience with digital reading materials. As noted by Patton (2002), purposive sampling is an effective technique in qualitative research as it focuses on information-rich cases that can provide valuable insights into the research questions. The sample included an equal distribution of students across the first to fourth year levels.

Instrument

The primary instrument for data collection was a semi-structured interview guide, developed to elicit detailed responses about participants' digital reading experiences. The guide included open-ended questions that prompted discussions about reading frequency, duration, comprehension, and perceptions of digital texts. To ensure reliability and validity, the interview guide was reviewed by experts in qualitative research and revised based on their feedback (Creswell, 2013).

Procedure

The data collection process involved conducting individual interviews with each participant. Prior to the interview sessions, informed consent was obtained, ensuring that participants understood the study's purpose and their right to withdraw at any time. The interviews were conducted in a quiet and comfortable setting to facilitate open communication. Each session was recorded and later transcribed for analysis. Thematic analysis was employed to identify patterns and themes within the data, following the steps outlined by Braun and Clarke (2006). This systematic approach enabled the researchers to interpret the data meaningfully and draw relevant conclusions.

Ethical Considerations

The importance of ethical considerations has increased recently among the research community. This is partly a consequence of a legislative change in human rights and data protection, but also a result of increased public concern about the limits of inquiry (Roberts, 2003). With that to be considered, the researchers adhered to the safety of the participants and informants as the measure of the research is concerned. Participants were informed about the study's objectives, and their confidentiality was ensured by anonymizing their responses. Participation was voluntary, and students were given the option to withdraw from the study at any time without any consequences. Additionally, the research obtained approval from the college's ethics review board, ensuring compliance with institutional guidelines for conducting research with human subjects (Creswell, 2013).

Results and Discussion

This section presents the outcome of the qualitative analysis of the research questions answers. The results are presented based on the emerging themes and core ideas.

Profile of the Conversational Partners

The findings of the study are presented in Matrices generated from the thematic analysis.

Table 1. *Profile of the Participants*

Category	Assumed Name	Gender	Location	Level	Study Group
DRBTAEMS_P1	Anonymous	Male	Davao City	4th Year	Interview
DRBTAEMS_P2	Vev	Female	Davao City	4th Year	Interview
DRBTAEMS_P3	Shiela	Female	Davao City	4th Year	Interview
DRBTAEMS_P4	Momma Cho	Male	Davao City	4th Year	Interview
DRBTAEMS_P5	The Legendary	Male	Davao City	4th Year	Interview
DRBTAEMS_P6	Burakdat	Female	Davao City	3rd Year	Interview
DRBTAEMS_P7	Pawi	Male	Davao City	3rd Year	Interview
DRBTAEMS_P8	Carlos Ibarra	Male	Davao City	3rd Year	Interview
DRBTAEMS_P9	Mikey	Male	Davao City	3rd Year	Interview
DRBTAEMS_P10	Dared	Female	Davao City	3rd Year	Interview
DRBTAEMS_P11	Ann Marie	Female	Davao City	2nd Year	Interview
DRBTAEMS_P12	Evie	Female	Davao City	2nd Year	Interview
DRBTAEMS_P13	Enzie	Male	Davao City	2nd Year	Interview
DRBTAEMS_P14	Ms. SA	Female	Davao City	2nd Year	Interview
DRBTAEMS_P15	Pikot	Male	Davao City	2nd Year	Interview
DRBTAEMS_P16	Langga	Female	Davao City	1st Year	Interview
DRBTAEMS_P17	Ejay	Female	Davao City	1st Year	Interview

DRBTAEMS_P18	Sansai	Female	Davao City	1st Year	Interview
DRBTAEMS_P19	Kulot	Female	Davao City	1st Year	Interview
DRBTAEMS_P20	Yanna	Female	Davao City	1st Year	Interview

Table 1 is the information of the participants in our study. The study involved 20 participants, all of whom were English major students enrolled at St. John Paul II College of Davao for Academic Year 2022-2023, aged 18 years and above. They were selected using purposive sampling to ensure relevant experience with digital reading materials. The participants were evenly distributed across year levels, with 5 students from each level (1st year to 4th year), comprising 15 females and 5 males. All participants were given pseudonyms to maintain confidentiality. Table 1 below summarizes the profile of the participants.

It is essential to highlight that strict ethical guidelines were followed during data management to safeguard the participants' privacy and confidentiality. Any concerns about keeping their information private were carefully handled, and we reported the data in a way that protected their identities. To prevent any gossip, rumors, or criticism from readers, we allowed the participants to use pseudonyms (fictitious names) while keeping the important context of the research.

Table 2. *Themes and Core Ideas of How Extent of the Reading Behaviour of the English Major Students on Digital Materials*

<i>Themes</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>
Cognitive Enhancement	Enhance academic knowledge, academic tools, academic profession, entertainment and vocabulary Have access, collect, and organize vast amount of information from a variety of website Find the meaning of the word for academic writing Serves as guidelines to academic lesson Utilizing audio reading, and reading different stories of literature and novels
Timeline of Reading	Three times a week, 40 minutes a day, 1 to 3 hours per day for reading literary books Twice a week and not more that five times 30 minutes for academic, 30 minutes for music 30 minutes in a day during class and vacant time 20 minutes a day and it will exceed if it is exam/task 1 hour for entertainment per day and 3 to 4 times a week 1 hour for academic and 6 hours for entertainment 2 hours for reading novel books Five hours per day It takes an hour in order to understand Every week due to Thesis Continuous if it is interesting story or article and finding information for making lesson plan Not prefer to read, not exceed to hour
Enormous Supplemental Learning Materials	Develop and improve reading comprehension Seek resources for academic essentials Attracts attention if it's interesting Acquire learning through different sources Content standard Navigate text to comprehend Learn to seek credible information Attract through the title of the story Reading inspirational books to enlighten life Because it is less hassle and handy
Improved Learning	Digital reading is more effective for doing research Digital reading can improve reading comprehension Digital reading help to understand single topic Digital reading allows readers to learn new words Digital reading can enlighten mind easily, accessible
Accessibility	Broader exploration and multi-source in research Effective, organize and quick access of desired information Accessible, Convenient, Flexible Information-rich Availability to skip page Unlock unfamiliar words Handy, Hassle- free

We started our interview process with English majors in order to learn more about the fundamental reasons for the utilization of internet resources. We specifically sought to determine the purpose of their use of these materials, including whether it was primarily for educational, recreational, or growth-related purposes, capabilities and professional skills. Through exploring their perspectives and experiences, we tried to identify the various elements affecting their actions in digital content, highlighting the complex character of their interaction with these resources.

Participants frequently noted that digital reading provided ease of access to materials and allowed for multitasking. One participant shared, “ I can access multiple books or articles with just my phone. It saves time and effort compared to carrying physical books. (DRBTAEMS_P-12)”. Participant emphasized the convenience of accessing digital materials anytime, noting that it enhances flexibility in their study routines. Our participant Enzie expresses that his intention for engaging in digital reading is to access various websites that can provide him with additional articles, journals, and information to gather and organize easily. “The purpose of my digital reading behavior is for academic, in terms of digital reading I can access many websites then it can to help me find more articles (DRBTAEMS_P-13).” He reads digitally to gather a significant amount of information, which is particularly beneficial for his studies. Therefore, he engaged in digital reading for academic purposes, where he acquired knowledge relevant to his studies. By reading digitally, English major students can access a wide range of materials, including books, articles, and online resources, which can enrich their understanding of various subjects. They understand that reading for enjoyment can also indirectly contribute to their academic growth.

Moreover, this participant said, “First and foremost, one of the advantages of reading on digital platforms is the ability to gather information more easily and understand it better. Additionally, it is convenient because it can be accessed on handheld devices such as phones or tablets. This accessibility is particularly useful when you are in a different location and don't want to carry physical books with you. Instead, you can simply use your phone to browse and search for the stories or information you are interested in, allowing you to quickly find the content you want to read or gather (DRBTAEMS_P17)” This aligns with the shift toward mobile reading technologies and their potential to facilitate learning in flexible environments. The convenience and accessibility of digital reading platforms truly revolutionize the way we access and consume information. It's remarkable how a single device, such as a phone or tablet, can serve as a gateway to a vast world of knowledge and captivating stories. Accessibility is one of our themes that defined by English major students: broader exploration and multi – source in research; effective, organized and quick access of desired information; accessible, convenient, flexible; information – rich; availability to skip page; unlock unfamiliar words; handy, hassle-free.

Table 3. *Themes and Core Ideas of How the Electronic Instructional Materials Improves the Reading Behaviour of English Major Students*

<i>Themes</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>
Advantage and Disadvantage of Digital Materials	Worldwide access, free, effective in improving teaching skills Improve practicing skills, reading comprehension and vocabularies Consequence for Non-compliance, Goal-oriented Behavior Gather more details of information Convenient and can read in the dark places Available and easy to use anytime Easy to navigate Any website can access an unlimited number of sources Updated learnings and information Effective, and feasible in real-life situations Allow to read in dark area, read anywhere, and informative Fast and quick access of title of the stories Advance and trend nowadays Broad information, unlimited search Able to read anytime Effective and informative Easy to read and less hassle Unlimited source of books Easy to scan and find books Can download tons of books in one click Browse unlimited stories and informative Comfortable to use the gadgets
Facile	Worldwide access, free, effective in improving teaching skills Improve practicing skills, reading comprehension and vocabularies Gather more details of information Convenient and can read in the dark places Available and easy to use anytime Easy to navigate Any website can access an unlimited number of sources Updated learnings and information Effective, and feasible in real-life situations Allow to read in dark area, read anywhere, and informative Fast and quick access of title of the stories Advance and trend nowadays Able to read anytime

	Effective and informative Easy to read and less hassle Unlimited source of books Easy to scan and find books Can download tons of books in one click Can edit and customize objects Browse unlimited stories and informative Comfortable to use the gadgets Broad information, unlimited search Able to read anytime Effective and informative Easy to read and less hassle Unlimited source of books Easy to scan and find books Can download tons of books in one click Can edit and customize objects Browse unlimited stories and informative Comfortable to use the gadgets
Digital Gaps	Lack of internet connection, access, unable to search some words, and too much ads Difficulties of maintaining concentration Requires payment to browse the whole article Unstable internet connection and quality of the content Limitation of online access Not able to function effectively Website that contains disinformation Extreme advertisement
Loosen Up	Small size of letters and words Listening to music and relax Eating snacks and read repeatedly Take breaks, Relax, Be comfortable and black mode, Bigger font size, simple font style Drink water and have low light exposure By means of sleeping

Electronic instructional materials have the potential to significantly improve the reading behavior of English major students. English major students improve their reading behavior by the advantages and disadvantages of digital materials, facile, digital gaps and loosen up. The root codes and branch codes on electronic instructional that improves the reading behavior of English major students is illustrated in this matrix. However, the allure of easy access often led to distractions. The Legendary, one of our participants, stated that it did not improve her interest in reading since she found it very dull and she easily get distracted when she read in digital materials. She continued in saying: “While you are browsing your digital book or whatever you are reading in digital you also access other apps in your phone for example. So, if you are reading right now 1 minute or 2 you are actually scrolling in your Facebook (DRBTAEMS_P5).” This narrative underscores the need for interventions that address screen-related discomfort and help students develop strategies to minimize distractions.

Yanna also expressed that she struggles reading when the letters are small. She continued uttering, “For this situation, if I easily get distracted, especially when the letters are small, it easily gives me a headache. That's a struggle for me, but specifically for academics, the materials are only available online, which I can manage but it's still a struggle because it can cause physical discomfort. It's not easy, but yeah, it's definitely a struggle (DRBTAEMS_P20).” Despite their capability to handle reading materials online, it still poses a significant challenge for them because it causes discomfort. This discomfort, which includes physical discomfort and headaches, makes it difficult for them to engage with the content effectively. They experience ongoing struggles and find it challenging to focus and comprehend the information presented in small letters.

Sansai, on the other hand, listens to music while reading. Listening to music can greatly help with focus and motivation while reading. “My coping mechanism while reading using digital platforms is listening to music. It helps me stay engaged and motivated, and I don't feel tired or bored when I have music playing in the background (DRBTAEMS_P18).” Music may serve as a background stimulation during solitary activities like reading, fostering an atmosphere that is favorable for focus.

Table 3. Themes and Core Ideas of How Suggestions/ Recommendations of the English Major Students that they Could Share to their Classmates in a Positive Reading Behaviour

Themes	Core Ideas
Calibrate Learning Strategies	Reading on a digital device enables you to read more effectively Focus and look for some sources Be patient and understand the lesson Learn to love reading More photo is better in reading

	Determination and perseverance
	Maintain a positive attitude and go with the flow
	Brainstorm and sharing of ideas
	Keep entertain when reading because it is fun
	Practice more on reading to enhance vocabulary words
	Recommend to others
	Understand the subject thoroughly
	Read directly to the point words
	Read in a peaceful place
	Push yourself to read and enjoy
	Take some notes for retention
	Work under pressure
Motivate Oneself to Learn	Discuss the advantages, benefits, and how practical reading instructional material
	Tell them that reading is important and that they should push themselves to do so
	Tell them to read and understand to entertain
	Telling the positive impacts of digital reading
	Read with more pictures to keep interested
	Read to become fluent in English
	Understand what you're reading so that you can enjoy it
	Encourage them to highlight some words while reading so that it is enjoyable for them
	Encourage disinterested readers to explore
	Showing some links for them to access the reliable
Explore Possibilities in Learning	Expressing preferred genres for entertainment values
	Gaining knowledge
	Balance print and e-books for benefits
	Creating instructional resources
	Engage through graphics, editing, and conversation
	Boosting academic with knowledge and deeper understanding
	Correct pronunciation ability
	Improve language skills and cognition
	Provide convenience and affordable access
	Read consistently for efficiency
	Acquiring knowledge
	Learning collaboratively
	Expand reading comprehension, behaviour and vocabulary
	Take some notes for retention
	Improves skills and pronunciation
	Emphasize self-awareness in addictive effects
	Boost reading habits
	Boost language, thinking and creatively
	Offers easy access to vast reading materials
	Enables easy access to knowledge
	Diverse knowledge effects
	Provides analysis and communication
	Convenient reading is addictive
	Real life stories are intriguing
	Prefers print over digital
	Encourage reading for more knowledge
	Minimize gaming by self- discipline
	Encourage early exposure for knowledge
	Promote e-reading for vast information access
	Develop good reading habits through regular reading and book selection
	Developing time management skills and responsibility
	Focus on gaining knowledge and effort for reading
	Focus and use resources to support learning
	Motivates learning new phrases
	Choose own reading style for better understanding
	Choose own reading style for better understanding
	Analyzing and understanding reading content
	Prioritizing reading for personal growth and effective teaching content
	Emphasizing peaceful reading environment content

Students majoring in English describe many ways to improve their digital reading experience through the use of calibrated learning strategies. Through the use of technology and the internet, people can become more skilled at navigating and understanding digital texts and enhance their digital reading abilities.

One of our participants named, Momma Cho, expressed that she doesn't consider herself exceptionally intelligent, and she is simply fulfilling the necessary requirements to graduate, just like any other student, she added: "Maybe my determination and my perseverance and studying, like I'm not aiming for high grades I'm not aiming for anything but as much as I learn something, it's okay with me (DRBTAEMS_P4)."

Moreover, the participant said that regarding with this matter she will explain what the most advantage in reading using electronic books. "This is a new way of reading because we used to read through physical or printed books, right? So, first, I will explain to them that it's very convenient because all you need to do is, for example, when you are waiting for someone or waiting for your class, you can use your phone to browse and read. The information is easily accessible compared to printed books. I'm not saying that we should stop reading printed books, but for me, digital is more easily accessible because you can access it anywhere as long as you have an internet connection. (DRBTAEMS_P17)." the participant consider convincing others to utilize E- Books based on their preferred learning styles.

Books can be downloaded and accessed instantly from anywhere, making them more convenient than physical books. The Legendary added: "It influenced my reading behavior like it's not in a negative way since I get stubborn scrolling some or comprehending more idea because it will already be given in the digital materials. I find it there is no improvement in my reading when it comes to those reading materials, digital reading materials. I during our thesis we are more focused on the traditional books because it more reliable and we can assure that all the authors there are legit and authentic. So, we are more focused on gathering information in traditional book than to digital or online (DRBTAEMS_P5)."

Exploring possibilities in learning begins with an open mind and a thirst for knowledge. It means challenging traditional notions of education and seeking out alternative approaches that resonate with our unique learning styles and preferences.

The study revealed variations in preferences, with some students favoring e-books for flexibility and customization while others preferred the tactile experience of physical books. This chapter emphasized the need for educators to adapt instructional strategies to incorporate digital reading and support students in developing critical digital literacy skills. It also highlighted the importance of designing user-friendly digital platforms and fostering a reading culture that integrates both digital and print resources.

Overall, the interview results from the selected participants support the study, emphasizing the need for accommodating diverse preferences and promoting effective digital reading practices in education.

This study revealed several key aspects of digital reading behavior among English major students, emphasizing its cognitive, behavioral, and practical implications. Digital reading enables students to conveniently engage with diverse and extensive resources, aligning with the findings of Kosakiewicz (2017), which state that cognitive engagement through digital texts enhances comprehension and fosters critical thinking. Similarly, Cho (2014) highlights the cognitive techniques utilized by online readers, such as analyzing text placement, constructing meaning, and evaluating information, which further supports the development of critical thinking in digital contexts. The accessibility of digital platforms also allows students to navigate between academic and non-academic sources efficiently, helping them improve their reading comprehension and vocabulary acquisition through supplemental materials. The accessibility of digital platforms also allows students to efficiently navigate between academic and non-academic sources, helping them improve their reading comprehension and vocabulary acquisition through supplemental materials. Soroya and Ameen (2016) observed that the availability of electronic devices has increased the frequency and duration of reading activities, which has improved overall engagement and comprehension. This shift in reading habits corresponds with their findings.

Students identified motivation and adaptability as crucial elements of effective digital reading habits, as noted by Croft and Davis (2010), who reported that a lack of familiarity with digital reading can be a significant barrier. Similarly, Akçapnar et al. (2019) emphasized that features such as bookmarks, highlights, and search functions in e-books can foster greater engagement by allowing students to interact more deeply with digital texts. Moreover, Soroya and Ameen (2018) observed that the flexibility of digital reading platforms, especially with their portability and instant accessibility, was a significant motivational factor, helping students maintain interest and adaptability in various learning environments.

The research underscores the challenges of digital reading, such as screen fatigue and reduced focus on longer texts, echoing findings by Soroya and Ameen (2018) on the impact of online reading habits on concentration. Some students also mentioned distractions from notifications and advertisements as factors that affected their engagement with digital texts. Similarly, Cho and Afflerbach (2017) noted that students employ various strategies to maintain coherence and understanding despite these challenges. Despite these drawbacks, students generally viewed digital reading as a positive tool that complemented traditional methods by offering diverse perspectives and convenient access to information, consistent with observations by Chen et al. (2014) on the use of digital platforms to enhance engagement and comprehension.

In the end, the study's conclusions show that in order to help students use technological resources effectively, digital literacy activities are necessary. Including digital reading techniques in the curriculum can improve the children's academic achievement and encourage a love of learning that lasts a lifetime. Students have shown that cultivating a flexible and resilient attitude to digital reading can promote regular usage of digital texts, supporting a well-rounded reading strategy that takes into account combining print and digital preferences.

Conclusions

Recent years have seen a shift in how English major students engage with digital reading resources, relying on these platforms to access information and complete academic tasks. The study reveals that digital materials offer cognitive benefits, allowing students to deepen their academic knowledge and vocabulary.

This study highlights the themes and insights related to students' cognitive engagement, flexibility in reading, and resource accessibility. As observed by Kosakiewicz (2017), cognitive skills such as comprehension, critical thinking, and attention span are essential in digital reading, shaping how students navigate and absorb information in a digital format. English major students are eager to use these skills to improve their understanding and make the most of digital resources where students reported that digital reading platforms allow them to explore and manage a wide variety of learning materials with ease, repeating findings by Soroya and Ameen (2016) on the increased duration and frequency of reading through digital devices. They engage with diverse resources—from e-books and academic journals to multimedia content—that enrich their educational experience and offer them on-demand access to information. This flexibility aids their academic and personal growth, promoting continuous learning and skill development.

However, digital reading also presents challenges, including screen fatigue, distractions, and occasional information overload, which can impact students' comprehension and retention of content. Indah et al. (2022) emphasize the significance of helping students overcome these obstacles through digital literacy programs that encourage targeted and productive digital reading habits. These programs could teach kids to use internet resources more carefully and assist them in creating coping mechanisms for digital distractions.

To further enhance the outcomes, as suggested by Davidson and Coombe (2023), educators and institutions could think about integrating digital literacy into the curriculum to further improve the results. This will encourage abilities like digital annotation and information evaluation. By encouraging these abilities, educational institutions may help students develop into flexible, reflective, and technologically proficient individuals who are ready to take advantage of the opportunities presented by the huge digital world.

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